

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF AIRFOIL PERFORMANCE WITH TUBERCLES AND GURNEY FLAPS USING MESH-INDEPENDENT CFD SIMULATIONS

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Abstract- This study investigates the aerodynamic performance of a NACA 2412 airfoil using two passive flow control methods — leading-edge tubercles and surface dimples. Steady-state CFD simulations in ANSYS Fluent implemented on the airfoils with SST $k-\omega$ model. The angles of attack (AoA) were 0° , 4° , and 8° for baseline and other two models. Mesh independence verified at 0° AoA using four grids. An optimal mesh size of 1.6M to 2.1M elements was selected after drag coefficient variation fell below 1.5%. At 0° AoA tubercles improved lift-to-drag ratio by 7.3% over baseline (21.67 vs. 20.20). Dimples reduced it by 45.3% (11.05). At 4° , tubercles acted same as baseline ($L/D=47.29$ vs. 47.79 baseline). Dimples dropped L/D by 43.7% at 4° . At 8° , baseline achieved $L/D=47.16$. Tubercles decreased by 10.6%, and dimples by 45.4%. Results indicate tubercles can sustain aerodynamic efficiency at low-to-moderate AoA. But it can also cause drag penalties at higher AoA. Dimples consistently increased drag and reduced L/D . These outcomes offer valuable design insights for passive flow control method on airfoil.

Keywords: Passive flow control, Leading Edge Tubercles, Surface Dimples, Airfoil, Lift-to-drag ratio.

1. INTRODUCTION

Passive flow control on airfoils is a geometric modification that offers a promising route to enhance aerodynamic performance. Different passive flow control methods have been implemented for a long time. Among these, leading-edge tubercles and surface dimples draw interest from biomimetic inspiration and surface roughness strategies. Tubercles are inspired by humpback whale flippers. It introduces sinusoidal waves along the leading edge. Experimental investigation by Sudhakar et al. on a NACA 4415 airfoil revealed how tubercles break up laminar separation bubbles into smaller pockets [1]. This phenomenon also stabilizes flow and sustains lift into post-stall regimes. Numerical studies have also shown that tubercles create streamwise vortices that energize the boundary layer. It delays stalls and contributes to more gradual post-stall behavior [2]. In contrast, surface dimples act primarily as turbulent flow promoters through controlled surface roughness. Surface dimples can be seen commonly in golf balls. Recent reviews on flat-plate dimples indicate mixed evidence. Some studies report reductions in turbulent drag [3], and some warn of increased pressure drag offsetting any frictional gains [4]. This study evaluates the aerodynamic performance of a NACA 2412 airfoil with two passive flow control modifications—leading-edge tubercles and surface dimples. These two modifications were compared to a

smooth baseline. The work aims to quantify their impact on lift-to-drag ratios. This study will also find the drag characteristics to provide design-relevant insights for low-to-moderate angles of attack.

2. RECENT RESEARCH ON LEADING EDGE TUBERCLES AND SURFACE DIMPLES IMPLEMENTED ON AIRFOIL

Table 1: Recent Research on Leading edge tubercles and surface dimples.

Passive Control Method	Reported Effect	References
Leading-edge tubercles	Stall angle delayed $\approx 40\%$. Improved lift/drag behavior. The author measured increases in lift and reductions in drag for the scale flipper model	[5]
Leading-edge protuberances: 2D airfoil tests	Post-stall lift increases up to $\approx 50\%$. Greater than baseline for some geometries. lift decreases by around 20% and drag increase up to 70% for	[6]

	some modified foils	
Tubercles on rotors	Small performance gains reported for rotating blades. Thrust coefficient increases \approx 1.5–3%	[7]
Surface dimples on lifting surface (wing)	Drag coefficient reduced to 6.6% for best dimple configuration. L/D increase up to \approx 9.3%	[8]
Dimples / non-smooth surfaces	Some configurations report drag reductions up to \approx 40% in specialized setups.	[9]

Table 1 summarizes key findings from recent studies on leading-edge tubercles and surface dimples. They both serve as passive flow control methods. Leading-edge tubercles primarily improve post-stall lift behavior. It can delay stall by up to 40%. Some 2D airfoil studies shows that lift can increase up to 50%. Although drag penalties are reported for certain geometries.

Surface dimples generally act to reduce drag. Study shows that reductions can be up to 6–40% depending on configuration and surface. Overall, tubercles mainly enhance lift characteristics, especially near stall. While dimples are more effective for drag control. These trends justify investigating both methods on the NACA 2412 airfoil in this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the modeling procedures to evaluate the aerodynamic performance of a NACA 2412 airfoil. It includes details of the airfoil geometry, modeling of the passive flow control modifications, mesh dependency study, boundary conditions, solver settings, and simulation cases.

3.1 Geometry and Passive Flow Control Modifications

The base geometry of the airfoil was a NACA 2412 profile. It was created in SolidWorks using standard airfoil coordinates. The 3D model had a chord length (c) of 1 m and a span of 1 m. The baseline airfoil was exported as an IGES file. It was then imported to ANSYS DesignModeler for domain creation.

Two passive flow control modifications were applied to the baseline geometry:

- Leading-edge Tubercles:** Tubercles were introduced as sinusoidal protrusions along the leading edge. The tubercles had an amplitude (A) of 0.08 m and a wavelength (λ) of 0.1 m. Thus, 10 tubercles were spanning in the 1 m wing span. The modification was applied directly to the leading edge of the NACA 2412 airfoil and exported as a separate IGES model for simulation.
- Surface Dimples:** Each dimple had a diameter (D) of 0.02 m. The dimples were arranged in 9 chordwise rows. Each row contains 26 dimples with a spacing of 0.4 m. This dimpled model was also exported as a separate IGES file.

All geometries were prepared to maintain smooth surfaces. These CAD models were imported into ANSYS Fluent via DesignModeler.

Fig.1: 3D Model of (a) Baseline NACA 2412 airfoil, (b) Leading Edge Tubercles, (c) Surface Dimples.

3.2 Mesh Dependency Analysis

The baseline NACA 2412 model was simulated at 0° angle of attack under steady-state conditions in ANSYS Fluent. A mesh-independence study was performed on the baseline NACA 2412. AoA was at 0° and used four meshes (1.607M, 2.057M, 2.127M and 1.813M cells). Drag and lift from Fluent were converted to coefficients using wind velocity of 51.4496 m/s.

$$C_d = \frac{2D}{\rho V^2 A} \quad (1)$$

$$C_l = \frac{2L}{\rho V^2 A} \quad (2)$$

Here, $\rho = 1.1767 \text{ kg/m}^3$ [10] and $A = 1 \text{ m}^2$. The computed C_d values are 0.012369, 0.012183, 0.012156 and 0.012318 for Mesh1–Mesh4 respectively. It gives an overall spread of $\approx 1.74\%$ (min 0.012156, max 0.012369). The two finest meshes (Mesh2: 2.057M and Mesh3: 2.127M) differ by only $\approx 0.23\%$ in C_d value. It makes nearly identical L/D values between those 2 meshes. Figure 2 shows the production mesh (Mesh 3, 2,127,387 cells) with body-of-influence. The mesh includes 10 layers at the wall (first-layer thickness = 0.0025 m) and a surface element sizing of ≈ 0.025 m. Figure 3. shows the Mesh-convergence plot for the baseline NACA 2412 at 0° angle of attack. It shows drag coefficient C_d and lift coefficient C_L as a function of total mesh cell count (in millions).

Fig.2: Meshing for domain containing 2.127M cells.

Fig.3: Mesh convergence: Total cells vs. Cd and Cl (Baseline, 0° AoA)

3.3 Boundary Condition

The computational domain was designed to capture the aerodynamic behavior of the baseline and modified airfoils under various angles of attack. A velocity inlet of 51.45 m/s was applied at the upstream boundary. Turbulence intensity was 5 % at the inlet [10]. The outlet was set to a pressure-outlet condition with ambient pressure. Airfoil surfaces were treated as no-slip walls. The flow was considered steady and incompressible. Turbulence was modeled using the Realizable $k-\epsilon$ model. The domain extended sufficiently upstream and downstream of the airfoil to minimize boundary interference. Inlet positioned 2 m ahead of the leading edge and the outlet 4 m downstream of the trailing edge. Table 2 represents the core boundary condition applied to the simulations [10].

Table 2: Boundary conditions applied to Fluid Fluent

No.	Boundary Condition	Value
1	Fluid Medium	Air
2	Velocity of flow	51.4496m/s
3	Density of fluid	1.1767 kg/m ³
4	Chord length	1m
5	Span length	1m
5	Model	Realizable $k-\epsilon$
6	Angle of attack	0, 4, 8 degrees
7	Viscosity	1.009×10 ⁻⁵ kg/m.s
8	Temperature	277K

3.4 Simulation Cases and AoA Investigation

A total of twelve steady-state CFD simulations were performed to evaluate the aerodynamic performance of the NACA 2412 airfoil. Two primary passive flow control configurations were tested:

1. Baseline (no modification)
2. Leading-edge tubercles (amplitude 0.08 m, wavelength 0.10 m, 10 tubercles across span)
3. Surface dimples (diameter 0.02 m, depth 0.01 m inside and outside the surface, nine rows × 26

dimples per row, spacing 0.4 m)

Each configuration was assessed at 0°, 4°, and 8° AoA. The baseline 0° case, which underwent a four level mesh refinement study for mesh independence analysis. Mesh element counts ranged from 1.6 million for the coarsest baseline mesh to 2.1 million for the finest. Higher element counts used in dimpled configurations to adequately resolve small-scale surface features. Table 3 summarizes all the simulations performed for this study.

Table 3: Simulation Matrix with Mesh Details and L/D Ratios

Configuration	AoA (°)	Mesh Elements (Millions)	Purpose	L/D
Baseline	0	1.607	Mesh dependency	20.20
Baseline	0	2.057	Mesh dependency	20.43
Baseline	0	2.127	Mesh dependency	20.64
Baseline	0	1.814	Mesh dependency	20.83
Baseline	4	1.808	Performance study	47.98
Baseline	8	1.806	Performance study	47.14
Tubercle	0	1.604	Performance study	21.67
Tubercle	4	1.601	Performance study	47.28
Tubercle	8	1.600	Performance study	42.12
Dimple	0	2.175	Performance study	18.04
Dimple	4	2.181	Performance study	26.87
Dimple	8	2.173	Performance study	25.74

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Baseline Airfoil Performance

The baseline NACA 2412 airfoil was simulated at 0°, 4°, and 8° AoA to establish a reference for subsequent comparisons. The mesh independence study at 0° AoA (Table 4) demonstrated that changes in Cd between the finest two meshes were below 1%. It confirms the mesh convergence for this model. For the selected operational mesh (~1.8M elements), the L/D ratio increased from 20.20 at 0° to 47.98 at 4°. It was before slightly decreasing to 47.14 at 8° due to increased drag at higher AoA. Lift forces rose from 389.12 N at 0° to 1836.13 N at 8°. This increase reflects strong dependence on AoA. Figure 4 (a), (b), and (c) represent the baseline airfoil simulation result for different AoA.

Table 4: Baseline Performance Summary

AoA (°)	Cl	Cd	L/D	Lift (N)	Force Drag (N)	Force
0	0.6353	0.03145	20.20	389.12	19.26	
4	1.1832	0.02465	47.98	1153.40	24.13	
8	1.5657	0.03321	47.14	1836.13	38.94	

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.4: Contour of Pressure Coefficient Distribution Over the Baseline Airfoil at Various Angles of Attack (a) 0° (b) 4° (c) 8°

Figure 5, 6, 7 shows the variation of drag coefficients with number of cells and AoA for the baseline airfoil. It highlights the aerodynamic trends for various cell numbers.

Fig.5: Cd vs Number of Cells for baseline airfoil.

Fig.6: L/D vs AoA for baseline airfoil.

Fig.7: Cl vs AoA for baseline airfoil.

4.2 Tubercles vs. Dimple Comparisons

For modified airfoils, the tubercles and dimples significantly altered aerodynamic behavior compared to baseline.

At 0° AoA, tubercles produced a Cl of 0.570 and L/D of 21.67. It was slightly higher than baseline. This phenomenon indicates reduced drag without major lift penalty. Dimples showed a substantial lift increase (Cl = 0.996) but also higher drag (Cd = 0.0553). It lowers L/D to 18.04.

At 4° AoA, tubercles maintained high aerodynamic efficiency (L/D = 47.28) like baseline. But dimples suffered efficiency loss (L/D = 26.87) for increased drag. At 8° AoA, tubercles showed lift performance. But also showed 10.6% lower L/D than baseline. Dimples generated the highest lift (Cl = 1.987) but at the cost of ~45% lower L/D. Table 5 summarizes the comparison of baseline, tubercles and dimple with 3 separate AoA.

Table 5: Complete summary for the comparison of baseline, tubercles and dimple airfoil.

AoA (°)	Config	Cl	Cd	L/D	Lift (N)	Drag (N)
0	Baseline	0.6353	0.03145	20.20	389.12	19.26
	Tubercle	0.5700	0.02629	21.67	384.05	17.73
	Dimple	0.9960	0.05523	18.04	348.99	31.59
4	Baseline	1.1832	0.02465	47.98	1153.40	24.13
	Tubercle	1.1586	0.02449	47.28	1096.67	23.19
	Dimple	1.5711	0.05844	26.87	1052.78	39.17
8	Baseline	1.5657	0.03321	47.14	1836.13	38.94

AoA (°)	Config	Cl	Cd	L/D	Lift (N)	Drag (N)
	Tubercle	1.6333	0.03877	42.12	1703.77	40.40
	Dimple	1.9871	0.07716	25.74	1631.86	63.35

Figure 8 (a), (b), and (c) present the tubercle airfoil simulation results at AoA 0°, 4°, and 8°, respectively. It shows variations in pressure distribution, flow separation, and wake structure with increasing angle of attack.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.8: Contour of Pressure Coefficient Distribution Over the Tubercle Airfoil at Various Angles of Attack (a) 0° (b) 4° (c) 8°

Figure 9 (a), (b), and (c) shows the airfoil with dimple passive flow control method simulation results at AoA 0°, 4°, and 8°, respectively. It shows pressure coefficient with increasing angle of attack.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.9: Contour of Pressure Coefficient Distribution Over the Dimple Airfoil at Various Angles of Attack (a) 0° (b) 4° (c) 8°

4.3 Effect of Angle of Attack

Across all configurations, increasing AoA from 0° to 4° resulted in significant L/D gains for baseline and tubercle geometries. This effect happened because of increased lift while drag remained low. At 8° AoA, all configurations experienced drag rise. It reduced aerodynamic efficiency.

- Baseline: L/D improved by 137% from 0° to 4°. Dropped slightly (-1.7%) at 8° for drag increase.
- Tubercles: Showed similar trend. Only 10.9% L/D drop from 4° to 8°.
- Dimples: Across all AoAs, dimples showed higher lift. Dimples had poorer efficiency at 4° and 8°. It reflects higher pressure drag from surface indentations.

This simulated value indicates that tubercles offer balanced performance across AoAs. Dimples are advantageous where maximum lift is prioritized. Figure 10 demonstrates an overall comparison of Cl with angle of attacks.

Fig.10: Cl vs AoA for all configurations.

5. CONCLUSION

This study numerically investigated the aerodynamic effects of leading-edge tubercles and surface dimples on a NACA 2412 airfoil. They all were tested for angles of attack of 0°, 4°, and 8°. Mesh independence was

confirmed with <1% variation in Cd. The baseline airfoil achieved the highest aerodynamic efficiency at moderate AoA ($L/D = 47.98$ at 4°). Tubercles maintained comparable efficiency to baseline across all AoAs. Only a 10.9% drop in L/D from 4° to 8° . This indicates delayed performance degradation at higher AoA. Dimples consistently produced higher lift coefficients (up to $Cl = 1.987$ at 8°). It suffered efficiency losses (up to ~45% L/D drop) for increased drag.

Overall, tubercles are recommended for applications of balanced performance and stall delay. Dimples may be beneficial in designs that requires maximum lift despite efficiency trading-offs.

6. REFERENCES

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7. NOMENCLATURE

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
AoA	Angle of Attack	(degrees)
c	Chord length	(m)
A	Amplitude (for tubercles)	(m)
λ	Wavelength (for tubercles)	(m)
D	Diameter (for dimples)	(m)
ρ	Density	(kg/m ³)
A	Reference area	(m ²)
V	Velocity	(m/s)
Cl	Lift coefficient	Dimensionless
Cd	Drag coefficient	Dimensionless
L/D	Lift-to-drag ratio	Dimensionless
k	Turbulent kinetic energy	(m ² /s ²)
ω	Specific dissipation rate	(s ⁻¹)
ε	Turbulent dissipation rate	(m ² /s ³)